

Management Strategy of Brain Metastases in Lung Cancer

Esma Kerboua

Medical Oncology Department, Pierre and Marie Curie Center, Algiers, Algeria; University of Health Sciences, Algiers, Algeria

Kamelia Hannachi

Medical Oncology Department, Pierre and Marie Curie Center, Algiers, Algeria

Merzek Gharnaout

University of Health Sciences, Algiers, Algeria; Pulmonology and Phthisiology Department, Beni Messous University Hospital Center, Algiers, Algeria

Kamel Bouaita

Neurosurgery Department; Faculty of Medicine, Blida University, Blida, Algeria

Abstract

Brain metastases represent the most frequent intracranial complication of bronchopulmonary cancers. We retrospectively analyzed 120 patients with lung cancer–related brain metastases treated at the Pierre and Marie Curie Center, Algiers, between 2011 and 2023, to describe their clinical and therapeutic characteristics. The cohort included 100 men and 20 women, with a mean age of 62 years. Brain metastases were present at diagnosis in 78% of cases, detected during staging in 13%, and occurred metachronously in 9%, with a mean delay of 18 months. Most patients presented with solitary brain lesions (79%). Adenocarcinoma was the predominant histological subtype (64%), followed by squamous cell carcinoma (20%) and small-cell lung cancer (10%). Surgical resection and radiotherapy were performed in 17% and 40% of patients, respectively. Median overall survival was 12.75 months. Brain metastases remain a frequent and poor prognostic event in lung cancer, and management should be individualized according to disease burden, performance status, number of brain lesions, and tumor biology, ideally within a multidisciplinary framework.

Introduction

Brain metastases are a common and serious complication of bronchogenic carcinoma, most often presenting as multiple lesions. They occur in approximately 70–80% of patients with small-cell lung carcinoma (SCLC) and in 30–50% of those with non-small-cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC). About 10% of bronchogenic carcinomas are diagnosed simultaneously with brain metastases. These intracranial lesions have a major impact on prognosis, highlighting the critical importance of timely diagnosis and optimal multidisciplinary management.

Study Objective

To evaluate the epidemiological, clinical, and therapeutic characteristics of brain metastases secondary to lung cancer.

Materials and Methods

We conducted a retrospective study including 120 patients treated for bronchopulmonary cancer with brain metastases at the Medical Oncology Department of the Pierre and Marie Curie Center, Algiers, in collaboration with pneumophtisiology department Algiers, between January 2011 and December 2023.

Results

A total of 120 patients were included, comprising 100 men and 20 women, with a mean age of 62 years (range: 27–77 years). Brain metastases were the initial presentation of lung cancer in 94 patients, detected during staging workup in 16 patients, and occurred metachronously in 10 patients. The mean time to development of metachronous brain metastases was 18 months (range: 7–36 months) (see Figure 1).

More Information

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Figure 1: Clinical Presentation Patterns of Brain Metastases

Brain metastases were solitary in 95 patients (79%) and multiple in 25 patients (21%). Histopathological analysis revealed adenocarcinoma in 64% of cases, squamous cell carcinoma in 20%, small cell lung carcinoma in 10%, atypical carcinoid tumors in 3%, and large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma in 3%.

Surgical resection of brain metastases was performed in 20 patients (17%), while 48 patients (40%) received radiotherapy (see Table 1). The mean overall survival was 12.75 months (range: 2–44 months).

Table 1: Patients’ Characteristics

Number	120 patients
Sex	M 100 F 20
Age (Years)	
Median	62
Range	27-77
Brain Metastasis	Synchrouns 94 Staging assessment 16 Metachrounous 10
Histology	Adenocarcinoma 60% Squamous cell carcinoma 20%
Surgery	20 patients
Radiotherapy	48 patients

Discussion

Brain metastases represent frequent and severe complication of bronchopulmonary cancers and constitute the leading cause of brain metastases in adults. In our study, the population was predominantly male, with a mean age of 62 years, which is consistent with published data reporting that lung cancer–related brain metastases occur mainly in men aged between 55 and 65 years, reflecting the overall epidemiology of lung cancer [1,2].

In our series, brain metastases were the initial presentation of lung cancer in nearly 79% of cases. This rate is relatively higher than that reported in international studies, where concomitant diagnosis of brain metastases is described in 10–30% of cases, particularly in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) [3,4].

This discrepancy may be related to delayed diagnosis of thoracic disease, limited access to early screening, or a clinical presentation dominated by neurological symptoms.

Metachronous brain metastases were observed in a subset of patients, with a mean time to occurrence of 18 months. This finding is in line with literature data reporting a median interval of 12–24 months following the diagnosis of primary lung cancer, especially in NSCLC [5]. These results confirm that the brain remains a frequent site of disease progression despite initial treatment.

With regard to lesion number, solitary brain metastases were predominant in our cohort (79%), in contrast to several reports in which multiple lesions account for up to 60% of cases [6]. This may have contributed to the relatively high proportion of patients eligible for aggressive local treatments, including surgical resection.

Histologically, adenocarcinoma was the most frequent subtype (64%), followed by squamous cell carcinoma (20%) and small cell lung carcinoma (10%). This distribution is consistent with current evidence demonstrating a higher propensity for brain dissemination in adenocarcinoma and small cell lung carcinoma compared with squamous cell carcinoma [7,8]. The predominance of adenocarcinoma also reflects the evolving epidemiological trends of lung cancer.

From a therapeutic standpoint, surgical resection of brain metastases was performed in selected patients, mainly those with a solitary lesion and good performance status, whereas radiotherapy—predominantly whole-brain radiotherapy—was administered to a larger proportion of patients. These treatment strategies are in accordance with international guidelines, which recommend a multimodal approach based on the number of brain metastases, patient performance status, control of extracranial disease, and neurological symptoms [9,10]. Despite therapeutic interventions, overall prognosis remained poor, with a mean overall survival of 12.75 months. This outcome is comparable to survival data reported in NSCLC patients with brain metastases, where median survival ranges from 4 to 16 months depending on prognostic factors [11]. However, recent advances in systemic treatments, including targeted therapies and immunotherapy, have demonstrated improved intracranial disease control and survival, particularly in patients harboring actionable molecular alterations [12,13].

Finally, our study highlights the critical importance of a multidisciplinary approach involving medical oncologists, radiation oncologists, neurosurgeons, and radiologists to optimize therapeutic decision-making and improve patient outcomes.

Conclusion

Brain metastases are a common complication of bronchopulmonary cancers. Treatment strategies should be individualized based on the control of the primary thoracic tumor, the patient's performance status, the number of brain metastases, and the presenting neurological symptoms. The use of targeted therapies is further guided by tumor histology and the presence of predictive molecular biomarkers. All therapeutic decisions should be made within the context of a multidisciplinary tumor board to ensure optimal and personalized management.

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